

**Studying the life and work of Anvar Abidjan in extracurricular reading
classes**

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Аннотация: В данной научной статье описывается организация внеурочной деятельности, ее виды, этапы и формы, а также изучение жизни Анвара Обиджона, создателя бессмертных произведений, в форме открытого урока.

Ключевые слова: Основные формы внеурочной деятельности, система классных занятий, концепция, эстетическое мышление, сказки, инсценировка произведения.

Abstract: In this scientific article, the organization of extracurricular activities, their types, stages and forms, as well as the study of the life of Anvar Obidjon, the creator of immortal works, are described in the form of an open lesson.

Key words: The main forms of extracurricular activities, the class lesson system, concept, aesthetic thinking, fairy tales, dramatization of the work.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada sinfdan tashqari ishlarni tashkil qilish, ularning turlari, bosqichlari va shakllari hamda o‘lmas asarlar ijodkori Anvar Obidjonning hayot ijodini o‘rganish ochiq dars shaklida bayon qilinadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Sinfdan tashqari ishlarning asosiy shakllari, sinf dars tizimi, konsepsiya, estetik tafakkur, ertaklar, asarni sahnalashtirish.

It is not surprising that in Uzbek children's literature, the series of poems can be found most often in the work of Anvar Obidjon. Poems in such series as "Strange Letters", "Songs You Never Heard", "Amazing House", "Six Tales from Sixteen", "Botirvoy's Diary", "Nightingale's Nightingales" are his discoveries, childishly simple, sincere humor, short, fluent, playful verses, "puzzles" with two or more solutions that make children think, you are familiar to us. It is worth noting that, although written on a specific topic, a poem in one series does not repeat the content of another, on the contrary, a unique theme, form, language and style were chosen for each series. For example, in the series "Nightingale's Chopchaklari", poems in the form of ghazals are sung in the language of the Nightingale, with the aim of instilling love for Aruz in the young reader. In the "My needles are beautiful" series, it is aimed to further increase the feeling of respect, kindness, benevolence towards other members of nature through the biographies of various creatures. In the beginning of the "From the Fields to Children" series, which we are going to talk about, the poet appears in the eyes of the student as a journalist: "To be honest, I write poems just for fun. Actually, my profession is journalism. I was once a radio reporter. I wholeheartedly agree with those who say that it is pointless to take the microphone naked like Alpomish's sword and make people talk. But my achievement is that Musharraf was able to conduct dozens of interviews not only with people, but also with different crops and trees when I was walking around the fields. It is not surprising that this situation shocks the category of journalists, who are the mouth, eyes, ears and nose of the world." A short introductory word in the meaning of interpretation given after the title, on the one hand, unites the poems in the series around one theme,

and on the other hand, serves to mentally prepare the young reader for the poem to be read. In addition, he is an author who introduced delicate pichin (cut) poems to the creative Uzbek children's poetry. This is especially evident in his "Songs You Haven't Heard" series. Poems differ both in form and content. The discovery of the form is the imitation of the sounds, and the novelty of the content is intended to enrich the meaning of each poem. But at the same time, they help to complete the image of a person as a moral and psychological criterion:

Slipper song:

I walk in the house,

Ship-ship-ship.

The carpet is so soft

Ship-ship-ship.

I will not touch the stone,

Ship-ship-ship.

Sow hard to the sun,

Ship-ship-ship.

Also, the author skillfully uses the change of sounds (imitation words) and achieves imagery (such as chirping, chirping, chirping, whispering, rustling). It is not for nothing that this series of poems is called songs, because they are melodious. It is not difficult to imitate the characters of children and adults in the images of singers in the series. The poems are simple, but read in one breath. The poet uses words very sparingly. Light humor mixes with the reality of life and

increases the emotional-ideal impact on the reader. An example of how well the author can enliven allegorical images: Meet me, I study in the first "B" class, I can write all thirty-five letters well. Why do we write an X without a tail when we say rooster? Oh, you cockerel, you think the rooster has no tail! The poet animates animals and objects and reveals their characteristics. He correctly finds the specific characteristics of objects, human "virtues" and "flaws". Here, for example, is the letter written by the kora to Kumong. Everyone greets Kumgon. And the teapot raises its nose to the sky. Kora writes the following letter to Kumgon:

Burning in the oven,

You boil the water,

Put it on a plate

He respects the spirit. Even when the poet uses similes, he does not forget the child's psyche, he likens it to a familiar action or situation in order to explain an event or action. He gives students the first lessons of spirituality through a certain image. Each line of the beloved children's poet Anvar Obidjon carries a specific educational content. According to the State Standards and Curriculum of General Secondary Education, the children's motherland is based on the skills and competences formed in the literacy classes in the 1st grade. , ideas and concepts about independence and national values will be expanded and enriched. Extracurricular reading and recitation lessons are introduced to children's fiction in 20 minutes of lessons once a week in the 1st grade. The goal is to instill in young children a love for books, to develop independent reading. Mainly, the students of this class are taught the knowledge, skills and abilities of dealing with books, rules of reading books, keeping books, observing the behavior of the heroes of the work,

studying their positive aspects, retelling the story in a figurative way. For the students of this class, mostly books with pictures are taken. By reading books that develop children's emotions, the teacher introduces our independent country, its beautiful cities, villages, national traditions, values, past, and people's dreams. They have a passion for knowledge. In the 2nd grade, students read small works independently based on the teacher's help and assignment. In this class, extracurricular study is held once every 2 weeks.

The teacher finds and recommends to the students the works about Motherland and the bravery of the ancestors, plants, birds and animals. In the 4th grades, the lives of people are vividly described, their spiritual and moral way of life for the students' independent study. featured artistic and popular scientific works are recommended. In grades 3-4, extracurricular reading lessons are held once every two weeks. In these classes, the teacher continues to stock the classroom library with age-appropriate books. The study corner outside the classroom can be decorated in different ways. In this, the teacher and the student work together. Artistic and popular scientific works serve to expand and form the worldview of students only if they are read independently and consistently. Reading outside the classroom serves to instill in children love for goodness, hatred for evil, communication, speech development, and literary-aesthetic thinking. First of all, children's literature gives joy to children with its interesting content, the beauty of artistic images, the expressiveness of the language, the musicality of poetic words. At the same time, it also has an educational effect on children. Children's literature tells the reader about the nature of the country, people's work, life, their actions and heroism, stories from children's lives, children's games, dreams, dreams. In this regard, fairy tales are of great importance.

The history of our nation, its traditions, material and spiritual wealth, all dreams and wishes are preserved in fairy tales created for thousands of years. People want to see their dreams in the young generation in their sons and daughters. For this reason, students are recommended to read fairy tales. A child who reads a fairy tale tries to overcome difficulties, to be brave and courageous. A student can become a worthy child of his people only if he says that I am a part of all the people on earth, and I should grow up worthy of them by what I do for my people. Fairy tales are an international artistic tool that educates the young generation in this spirit.

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